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DNA barcoding and phylogenetic analysis of spider *Nephila pilipes* from Latehar, Jharkhand (India)

लातेहार, झारखंड (भारत) से प्राप्त *Nephila pilipes* मकड़ी का डीएनए बारकोडिंग एवं वंशानुक्रमिक विश्लेषण

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सारांश

ऊर्जा का एक ट्रॉफिक स्तर से दूसरे ट्रॉफिक स्तर में स्थानांतरण, मकड़ियों की सबसे महत्वपूर्ण पारिस्थितिक क्रियाओं में से एक है। ये शिकारी आर्थ्रोपॉड्स हैं जो खाद्य जाल में महत्वपूर्ण भूमिका निभाते हैं। चूंकि ये अनिवार्य शिकारी होते हैं, इसलिए ये विभिन्न प्रकार के जीवों का भोजन करते हैं, जिनमें अन्य मकड़ियां भी शामिल हैं। मकड़ियां कई कीटों की प्राकृतिक शिकारी होती हैं, जिनमें मच्छर, मक्खियां और कृषि कीट जैसे हानिकारक कीट शामिल हैं। इन कीटों का शिकार करके, मकड़ियां उनकी आबादी को नियंत्रित करने में मदद करती हैं, जिससे रासायनिक कीटनाशकों की आवश्यकता कम हो जाती है। यह न केवल पारिस्थितिक संतुलन बनाए रखने में मदद करता है, बल्कि बेहतर फसल उत्पादन का भी समर्थन करता है। *Nephila pilipes* पारिस्थितिक संतुलन बनाए रखने में महत्वपूर्ण भूमिका निभाती है, क्योंकि यह कीट नियंत्रण में योगदान देती है और जटिल खाद्य जाल का हिस्सा होती है, जहां यह पक्षियों, ततैयों और अन्य शिकारी जीवों के लिए भोजन का कार्य करती है। भारत के झारखंड राज्य में मकड़ियों का अध्ययन उपेक्षित रहा है और अब तक मकड़ियों से संबंधित कोई महत्वपूर्ण वैज्ञानिक योगदान नहीं हुआ है। इन्हीं कारणों से, यह अध्ययन, जो अपनी तरह का पहला है, *Nephila pilipes* का लेटहार वन (झारखंड) से रूप-आणविक (morpho-molecular) अध्ययन करने के लिए किया गया। झारखंड में पहली बार, किसी भी मकड़ी का रूप-आणविक विश्लेषण किया गया है। हम *Nephila pilipes* की उपस्थिति की रिपोर्ट लेटहार वन, झारखंड से प्रस्तुत करते हैं, जो रूपात्मक (morphological) तथा आणविक (CO1) दोनों विश्लेषणों पर आधारित है।

कुंजी: *Nephila pilipes*, मकड़ी, झारखंड, CO1 जीन, बारकोडिंग, GenBank, accession ID

Abstract

The movement of energy from one trophic level to another is one of the spiders' most significant interactions. They are predatory arthropods that play important role in the food web. Since they are obligatory predators, they feed on a wide range of creatures, including other spiders. Spiders are natural predators of many insects, including pests like mosquitoes, flies, and agricultural pests. By preying on these insects, spiders help to keep their populations in check, reducing the need for chemical pesticides. This not only helps in maintaining ecological balance but also supports healthier crop yields. *Nephila pilipes*, plays significant role in maintaining ecological balance by contributing to pest control, are part of complex food web, serving as prey for birds, wasps and other predators. In Jharkhand state of India, the study of spiders is neglected, and till now no significant scientific contributions related to spiders are not there. Thus, owing to these apprehensions, the present work, first of its kind, was undertaken to do the morpho-molecular study of *Nephila pilipes* from the Latehar forest, Jharkhand. For the first time from Jharkhand, we have performed morpho-molecular analysis of any of the spiders from Jharkhand. We report the presence of *Nephila pilipes* from Latehar forest of Jharkhand on the basis of both morphological as well as molecular (CO1) analysis.

Keywords: *Nephila pilipes*, spider, Jharkhand, CO1 gene, barcoding, GenBank, Accession ID

1. Introduction

A biological community is made up of all the species that live together in a certain area. One of the most important interactions among these species is the transfer of energy from one trophic level to another. As predatory arthropods in the food web, spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) are significant (Singh & Singh, 2021). As necessary predators, spiders consume a variety of organisms, such as other spiders and occasionally vertebrates. A spider is thought to be able to eat up to 2000 insects a year (Walker, 2010). Spiders are vital to

each community in which they dwell because they have the ability to regulate species densities on several levels. Indirectly, spiders benefit people by consuming a variety of pests, including aphids, grasshoppers, leafhoppers, beetles, and caterpillars (Maloney et al., 2003).

There is still a lack of information regarding the spiders of Jharkhand, despite recent studies on the diversity and distribution of spiders in India (Raji et al., 2024; Upadhyay and Das, 2024; Dave and Trivedi, 2024; Parmar, 2024; Meher et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2024; Saha et al., 2024; Zehbi and

Yousuf, 2024). In an effort to catalog the faunal variety of Jharkhand's spiders, Singh and Singh (2021) relied on published records, books, chapters, articles, and other materials on Jharkhand's spiders up to October 2021.

Nephila pilipes, sometimes referred to as the gigantic golden orb weaver or the northern golden orb weaver.

2. Materials and Methods

The results of a morpho-molecular analysis of *Nephila pilipes* collected from Jharkhand's Latehar forest are presented in this work.

Spider Sampling

Several samples of *Nephila pilipes* had been collected from the Latehar forest (23.739584, 84.539434) in Jharkhand. The spiders were collected and released after being identified using traditional morphological criteria of the specimen. One of the obtained samples was sacrificed in an insect killing jar with ethyl-acetate fumes (Kumar et al., 2022). One hind leg of the sample was detached and stored in 70% ethanol for DNA (deoxyribonucleic acid) extraction, PCR (polymerase chain reaction) amplification, and sequencing. The isolate sample was subsequently submitted to the Insect Collection Record and Identification (ICRI), Entomology specialization, Department of Zoology, St. Xavier's College, Ranchi, using voucher number SXCRAN-ENT-0923S07.

DNA extraction, PCR amplification and sequencing

DNA was extracted from the isolate's hindleg which was stored in 70% alcohol (SXCRAN-ENT-0923S07). The quality was assessed using a 1.0% agarose gel. A single band of high-molecular DNA was discovered. Fragments of the mitochondrial cytochrome subunit 1 (CO1) gene were amplified using particular forward and reverse primers. When resolved on an agarose gel, only one distinct PCR amplicon band of 617 bp was seen. The PCR amplicon was then processed to eliminate any impurities. The PCR amplicon was sequenced with forward and reverse primers using the BDT v3.1 cycle sequencing kit on an ABI 3730xl Genetic Analyzer (ThermoFischer, 2024).

Molecular sequence analysis tools

Using the Sanger sequencing approach, a distinct PCR amplicon was identified. The PCR amplicon was compared to data in the nucleotide database using the BLAST (Basic Local Alignment and Search Tool) tool available from NCBI (National Center for Biotechnology Information). A nucleotide BLAST option (BLASTn) was employed. BLASTn matches the nucleotide query (our sequence) to the topic sequences (those found in databases) (Srivastava et al., 2024).

Submission of nucleotide sequence to the GenBank

Based on the BLASTn results, the spider specimen was identified as *Nephila pilipes*. After confirmation, the CO1

nucleotide sequence was submitted to the DNA databank of Japan (DDBJ) and the accession id LC841772.1 was obtained for nucleotide sequence (617 bp).

The full definition of our CO1 sequence submitted to the DDBJ can be viewed by either visiting the link <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/LC841772.1/> or it may be accessed by scanning the QR (quick response) code presented as figure 1.

Figure 1: QR code can be scanned to obtain full definition of the CO1 nucleotide sequence (LC841772.1) of the *Nephila pilipes* collected from Latehar forest, Jharkhand

Phylogenetic tree and Distance Matrix

The top ten sequences were selected from the BLASTn search results page. An unrooted phylogenetic tree was constructed using the top 10 sequences and our CO1 sequence (Saitou and Nei, 1987). The evolutionary distances, which are given in base substitution units per site, were computed using the Maximum Composite Likelihood Method (Tamura et al., 2004). For each pair of sequences, paired deletion was done in all uncertain locations. MEGA X (Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis) version 10.2.6. build 10210527-x86_64 (Windows 11) was used for these investigations.

3. Results and Discussion

Morphological description

The body sizes of the investigated specimens varied from 29 to 49 mm in females and 5-6 mm in males. The species exhibits female gigantism and male dwarfism. The species has a significant size variation between male and female individuals (Kunter et al. 2012).

Figure 2: *Nephila pilipes* collected from Latehar forest, Jharkhand, India

The female's cephalothorax was approximately 15 mm length and 10 mm broad. The abdomen was 29mm long and 15mm broad, primarily dark yellow-brown with yellow streaks. The tergum was blackish dark and coated with thick hair. Both

rows of eyeballs protrude toward the back. The platypus was black. Long legs in black and yellow.

Figure 3: Diagram of *Nephila pilipes*

In females, the cephalothorax was around 2.5 mm length and 2 mm broad. The abdomen measured 4 mm length and 1.45 mm broad. Front eyes are bigger than rear eyes. Light brown legs with minimal hair. Yellow-colored carapace with hairs.

Figure 4: Photo of *Nephila pilipes* with asymmetric orb web in the background

Synonyms

- 2007, *Nephila maculata* Gajbe
- 2006, *Nephila maculata* Kim
- 1995, *Nephila maculata* Barrion & Litsinger
- 1991, *Nephila maculata* Chen & Zhang
- 1990, *Nephila maculata* Feng
- 1989, *Nephila maculata* Chikuni

- 1989, *Nephila maculata* Hu & Wu
- 1987, *Nephila maculata* Song
- 1986, *Nephila maculata* Wunderlich
- 1982, *Nephila maculata* Tikader
- 1980, *Nephila maculata* Levi
- 1967, *Nephila maculata* Wiehle
- 1960, *Nephila maculata* Chrysanthus
- 1959, *Nephila maculata* Chrysanthus
- 1959, *Nephila maculata* Saito
- 1915, *Nephila maculata* hasselti Hogg
- 1915, *Nephila maculata* walckenaeri Hogg
- 1912, *Nephila maculata* Dahl
- 1912, *Nephila maculata* lauterbachii Dahl
- 1911, *Nephila maculata* flavornata Merian
- 1911, *Nephila maculata* piscatorum Vis
- 1911, *Nephila pictithorax* Kulczyński
- 1906, *Nephila maculata* Bösenberg & Strand
- 1906, *Nephila maculata* novae-guineae Strand
- 1906, *Nephila submaculata* Strand
- 1901, *Nephila maculata* jalorensis Simon
- 1894, *Nephila maculata* McCook
- 1894, *Nephila maculata* Simon
- 1881, *Nephila maculata* annulipes Thorell
- 1877, *Nephila walckenaeri* Thorell
- 1872, *Meta ornata* L. Koch
- 1872, *Nephila aurosa* L. Koch
- 1872, *Nephila fuscipes* L. Koch
- 1872, *Nephila pecuniosa* L. Koch
- 1872, *Nephila procera* L. Koch
- 1872, *Nephila sulphurosa* L. Koch
- 1872, *Nephila tenuipes* L. Koch
- 1871, *Nephila chrysogaster* O. Pickard-Cambridge
- 1859, *Epeira chrysogaster* Doleschall
- 1859, *Epeira harpyia* Doleschall
- 1859, *Epeira hasseltii* Doleschall
- 1859, *Epeira walckenaeri* Doleschall
- 1857, *Epeira penicillum* Doleschall
- 1857, *Epeira walckenaeri* Doleschall
- 1847, *Nephila ornata* Adams
- 1841, *Epeira caliginosa* Walckenaer
- 1841, *Epeira chrysogaster* Walckenaer
- 1841, *Epeira doreyana* Walckenaer
- 1841, *Epeira fuscipes* Walckenaer
- 1839, *Nephila fuscipes* C. L. Koch
- 1815, *Nephila maculata* Leach
- 1805, *Epeira chrysogaster* Walckenaer
- 1802, *Aranea sebae* Walckenaer
- 1793, *Aranea maculata* Fabricius
- 1793, *Aranea pilipes* Fabricius
- 1781, *Aranea longipes* Fabricius

Distribution

Nephila pilipes thrives in moist conditions without direct sunshine. It is found in Japan, China, Vietnam, Cambodia, Taiwan, Malaysia, Singapore, Myanmar, Indonesia, Thailand, Laos, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, India, Nepal, Papua New Guinea, and Australia. It is found in most areas of India and is famed for its massive webs. It is among the biggest spiders in India. It feeds on flies, beetles, and small birds. Its bite is not dangerous to humans, but the sting produces discomfort,

swelling, and blistering for a day or two. It is active from September to December.

Molecular Sequence Analysis

A single PCR amplicon of 617 bp from the CO1 region was produced using a particular primer. The obtained sequence is provided below in the FASTA format.

>*Nephila pilipes*_Rnc_Jh

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atatttagtattggagcttgaccgctatagtaggacctgctataagagtttgattcg
gattgaattgggtcaagttggaagattattaggagatgacagttatataatgtaattg
ttacaggtcatgctttgtaataattttttatggtatacctatttaattgggggtttg
gtaattgattggtccttaataattagggctcctgatagctttcctcgcataaataa
ttaagatttgattattacccttcattattttattattattcatcaatagtagaata
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agggttaggtgcaggatgaactgtatatctccattagcttcttagaaggccatgctg
gaagatctgtagattttgctattttttacatttagcgggtgcttctcaattaggg
gctattaactttattcaacaatttaaatgcatcatatggaatatctatagagaaa
gttctttattgtatgactgtattgattactgctgtattacttttctaccagat
tagctgggtcaattacaatatttaactgatcgaaatttaatacttctttttgacct
tctg
```

The resulting nucleotide sequence (query) was compared to nucleotide databases using the NCBI-based BLASTn tool. The top ten sequences of *Nephila pilipes* from various regions (countries) were chosen from among all blast hits (as of September 3, 2024). Table 1 displays the chosen sequences, including the maximum score, total score, E value, percentage identity, accession length, accession ID, and country/region.

Table 1: Table showing top 10 sequences selected on the basis of BLASTn results

Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession	Country/Region
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1140	1140	0	100.00%	617	DQ779283.1	Taiwan, R.O.C
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1118	1118	0	99.35%	617	AY052594.1	Taiwan, R.O.C
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1112	1112	0	99.19%	844	KF433457.1	Hunan, China
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1112	1112	0	99.19%	617	DQ779270.1	Taiwan, R.O.C
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1112	1112	0	99.19%	617	DQ779235.1	Taiwan, R.O.C
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1112	1112	0	99.19%	1093	KF433577.1	Hunan, China
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1112	1112	0	99.19%	617	DQ779275.1	Taiwan, R.O.C
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1112	1112	0	99.19%	617	AY052592.1	Taiwan, R.O.C
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1112	1112	0	99.19%	617	AY052593.1	Taiwan, R.O.C
<i>Nephila pilipes</i>	1112	1112	0	99.19%	617	DQ779236.1	Taiwan, R.O.C

Figure 5: Multiple Sequence Alignment (MSA) chart showing degree of similarity and differences.

Eight of the selected ten nucleotide sequences are from Taiwan, Republic of China, while two are from Hunan, China. The maximum and total scores were between 1112 and 1140. Percentage identification ranged between 99.19% and 100.00%. These data indicate that the CO1 sequence of *Nephila pilipes* obtained from Latehar, Jharkhand (India) is extremely closely linked to the selected ten species based on their closeness to the species' CO1 sequences.

Figure 5 depicts the MSA (Multiple Sequence Alignment) chart of the chosen sequence, indicating the degree of similarity and differences.

Distance matrix and phylogenetic tree

The CO1 nucleotide sequence from the selected 10 strains of *Nephila pilipes* given in table 1 and the CO1 sequence of a *Nephila pilipes* specimen obtained in Ranchi were used to create a distance matrix using MEGA X software. In phylogeny, distance matrices serve as a non-parametric distance approach. The distances are then resolved to form a phylogenetic tree. Distance matrix techniques of phylogenetic analysis explicitly rely on a measure of 'Genetic distances' between the sequences under consideration (Mount, 2004).

All 11 of the sequences listed above had their FASTA-aligned sequences aligned using CLUSTAL-W alignment in MEGA X. A

distance matrix and phylogenetic tree were then generated using the methods of maximum likelihood, neighbor joining, and minimal evolution. For the phylogenetic test, the

bootstrap approach was used (Sautou and Nei, 1987). Table 2 below displays the distance matrix.

Table 2: Distance matrix scores showing the degree of relatedness between the CO1 sequences of 10 selected strains of *Nephila pilipes* and the CO1 sequence of *Nephila pilipes* specimen collected from Latehar, Jharkhand

Samples		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
<i>Nephila pilipes</i> _Rnc_Jh	1		0.000	0.007	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008
DQ779283.1:Taiwan_R.O.C.	2	0.000		0.007	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008
AY052594.1:Taiwan_R.O.C.	3	0.007	0.007		0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
KF433457.1:Hunan_China	4	0.008	0.008	0.002		0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
DQ779270.1:Taiwan_R.O.C.	5	0.008	0.008	0.002	0.003		0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
DQ779235.1:Taiwan_R.O.C.	6	0.008	0.008	0.002	0.003	0.003		0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
KF433577.1:Hunan_China	7	0.008	0.008	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003		0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
DQ779275.1:_Taiwan_R.O.C.	8	0.008	0.008	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003		0.003	0.003	0.003
AY052592.1:Taiwan_R.O.C.	9	0.008	0.008	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003		0.003	0.003
AY052593.1:Taiwan_R.O.C.	10	0.008	0.008	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003		0.003
DQ779236.1:Taiwan_R.O.C.	11	0.008	0.008	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	

*N.B.: The colours represents the degree of relatedness

The present study utilized mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (MT-CO1) sequences to analyze the genetic relationship of *Nephila pilipes* collected from Latehar forest, Jharkhand (GenBank Accession: LC841772.1), with the top 10 closest matches retrieved from NCBI BLASTn. Mitochondrial CO1 is a commonly used genetic marker in species identification and phylogenetic studies due to its high interspecific variability and conserved structure within species (Hebert et al., 2003). The study incorporated a distance matrix and three phylogenetic tree construction methods — Maximum Likelihood (ML), Neighbor-Joining (NJ), and Minimum Evolution (ME) — to elucidate genetic divergence and evolutionary relationships.

Distance Matrix Analysis

The pairwise genetic distance matrix (Table 2) demonstrates that the specimen from Latehar (LC841772.1) shows a zero distance (0.000) from DQ779283.1, a *Nephila pilipes* specimen from Taiwan, indicating complete sequence identity between these two samples. This strongly suggests either a recent common ancestor or even potential conspecificity. The next closest match is AY052594.1 (Taiwan), with a minimal divergence of 0.007, indicating a close phylogeographic relationship. Interestingly, all remaining samples — originating primarily from Taiwan and Hunan, China — show only minor divergence ranging between 0.002 and 0.008, implying that the *Nephila pilipes* populations from India, Taiwan, and China are part of a tightly knit genetic group. Such low divergence (<1%) typically falls within the intraspecific threshold, supporting the idea that these populations may belong to the same species despite being geographically separated (Hebert et al., 2004; Barrett & Hebert, 2005).

Phylogenetic Tree Analysis

The phylogenetic trees constructed via three different algorithms (ML, NJ, and ME) using MEGA X software further corroborate the insights from the genetic distance matrix.

Maximum Likelihood (Figure 6): This tree demonstrates robust clustering of the Latehar sample with DQ779283.1 and AY052594.1, suggesting close evolutionary relatedness. All sequences cluster into a well-supported monophyletic clade, reinforcing the species-level coherence of *N. pilipes* across East and South Asia. The tree shows moderate-to-high bootstrap support, indicating reliable tree topology.

Neighbor-Joining (Figure 7): The NJ tree produces a similar topology as the ML tree, with the Latehar isolate grouping closest with the Taiwanese sequences, particularly DQ779283.1. Branch lengths in the NJ tree reflect minimal divergence among most sequences, echoing the distance matrix results.

Minimum Evolution (Figure 8): ME method, known for emphasizing branch length parsimony, also aligns the Latehar sequence closely with Taiwanese accessions. All sequences form a compact cluster, indicating minimal evolutionary distance. Such results highlight the stability of relationships among these sequences regardless of the phylogenetic inference method used.

These consistent topologies across different tree-building algorithms underscore the robustness of the genetic similarity between the Indian and East Asian populations of *N. pilipes*.

Figure 6: Phylogenetic tree constructed using Maximum Likelihood method (MEGA X)

Figure 7: Phylogenetic tree constructed using the Neighbor-Joining method (MEGA X)

Figure 8: Phylogenetic tree constructed using the Minimum Evolution method (MEGA X)

Biogeographical and Evolutionary Implications

The low sequence divergence across samples from geographically disparate locations like India (Latehar) and Taiwan or China points to historical gene flow or a recent common ancestry of *N. pilipes* populations across the Indo-Malayan biogeographic realm. This could be explained by the species' ecological adaptability and ballooning behavior

(aerial dispersal using silk threads), which facilitates long-distance dispersal in juvenile spiders (Coddington et al., 1996).

The identical CO1 sequence between the Latehar and Taiwanese specimen (DQ779283.1) may suggest:

- **Recent colonization or introduction** between these regions, either through natural dispersion or anthropogenic means.
- **Incomplete lineage sorting**, where the mitochondrial genome has not diverged sufficiently to reflect geographic separation.
- **Low evolutionary rate** in the CO1 gene in *Nephila pilipes*, as is sometimes observed in other arachnid taxa (Barrett & Hebert, 2005).

This observed genetic homogeneity contrasts with other orb-weaving spiders, where substantial intraspecific divergence has been reported across biogeographical zones (Álvarez-Padilla et al., 2009).

Taxonomic and Conservation Considerations

The genetic data provide evidence that the *Nephila pilipes* specimen from Latehar represents a population that is genetically coherent with conspecifics from Taiwan and China. This supports its identification as *Nephila pilipes* and highlights the importance of integrating molecular data for accurate taxonomy, especially in morphologically conserved or cryptic species complexes.

From a conservation standpoint, the discovery of genetically similar populations across such a wide geographic range suggests population connectivity, which may buffer against localized extinctions. However, further studies involving nuclear markers and morphological data are necessary to rule out cryptic speciation and confirm panmictic status.

4. Conclusion

The comparative phylogenetic and genetic distance analyses reveal a high level of genetic similarity between the *Nephila pilipes* specimen collected from Latehar, Jharkhand, and its counterparts from Taiwan and China. The zero distance with one Taiwanese specimen and minimal divergence with others, supported by consistent phylogenetic trees, indicates either a shared recent ancestry or recent gene flow. This study underscores the utility of MT-CO1 as a robust molecular marker for resolving inter- and intra-specific relationships and contributes to a broader understanding of the biogeographic structure of *N. pilipes* populations.

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